

and of the swelling due to their proliferation.

The vein-swollings varied in width from 0.2 to about 1 mm, and in length from about 1 mm to more than 10 cm. The number varied among tillers and varieties. The average was 4.3 vein-swollings/tiller among the 794 tillers of 42 diseased hills of 18 rices examined.

Of the 1,099 vein-swollings examined, 82% were white or pale yellow; 2%, light brown; 6%, dark brown; and 10%, mixed (one portion pale yellow, the other, brown). The colors seemed to remain unchanged until the death of the rice plants.

The vein-swollings appeared on both leaf sheaths and blades of artificially

infected plants at about 3 weeks after inoculation.

Although vein-swollings are less conspicuous than other symptoms of ragged stunt disease – ragged or twisted leaves and malformed or twisted flag leaves – they appeared fairly consistently on the diseased plants, particularly during later growth. ❧

A new medium for multiplication of sheath blight pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani* (*Thanatephorus cucumeris*)

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A new rice sand medium was developed for multiplication of *R. solani* to infect rice through soil inoculation at the seedling stage. Two hundred grams of well-sieved river sand was put in 250-ml Erlenmeyer flasks and 40 ml of tap water was added. Rice grains at 1 to 5% levels were added, sterilized at 15 psi for 1 hour, and inoculated with a single *R. solani* sclerotium. The incorporation of rice grains at 5% level was optimum to obtain maximum mycelial growth and sclerotial production. By the 7th day maximum mycelial growth and sclerotial production had been attained. The rice sand medium was used at an inoculum level of 25% to artificially induce rice seedling infection. ❧

Relationships involved in the bacterial blight syndrome

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The bacterial blight syndrome in the tropics has three types of symptoms: leaf blight, kresek, and pale yellow symptoms. The kresek and leaf blight symptoms are distinct and independent of each other (i.e. individual plants may be infected by either kresek or leaf blight). The kresek-infected plants may serve as a

source of inoculum for secondary infection leading to leaf blight, while leaf blight infection may turn into kresek if plants are infected during early growth or if the variety is susceptible to bacterial

Seed-borne nature of sheath blight pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani* in rice

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Seed of the variety ADT 31, which is susceptible to sheath blight disease, were collected from a crop affected by sheath blight during 1975 kuruvai (June-Sept), 1975-76 thaladi (Oct-Jan), and 1976 navarai (Feb-May), and tested for the presence of *R. solani*. The presence of the pathogen in seed planted in Dixon Agar medium indicated its seed-borne nature. Isolation of the fungus from seeds ranged from 4 to 6.6%. Seed collected in the thaladi had the highest infection (6.6%) followed by those in navarai (5%) and kuruvai (4%). ❧

Effect of different soil types on rice seedling infection caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*

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Seedlings of ADT 31, which is susceptible to sheath blight infection caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, were raised in pots

filled with soils of various types: red, clay, sandy loam, laterite, alluvial, black, and sandy. The sheath blight pathogen was multiplied in a rice sand medium and inoculated at the 25% level. Seedling infection was less in sandy soil (29.3%) and black soil (40%). The maximum seedling infection was recorded in clay soil (78.6%) followed by that in red, alluvial, laterite, and sandy loam soils. ❧

Preliminary observations of brown spot and its control in rice in Peru

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During the 1976-77 rice season severe brown spot symptoms, similar to those caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae*, were observed in the variety Nylamp planted at several sites in Lambayeque.

A fungus was isolated from diseased leaves. The mycelium was cream-colored and produced spore-like structures. The isolate failed to sporulate in a medium that was appropriate for *H. oryzae*.

From the nature of lesions and the failure of the mycelium to sporulate, the symptoms observed on Nylamp seem to have been caused by a fungus belonging to the *Dematracea* group, similar to *H. oryzae*. ❧